

An Analytical Study of the Professional Commitment of Punjab Teacher Educators in Relation to their Monthly Earnings

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Correspondence e-mail:

pratibhatiwariup@gmail.com

Prativa Tiwari

Research Scholar,

Department of Education

& Community Service, Punjabi

University, Patiala, Punjab (India)

Abstract : The present study investigates the professional commitment of four hundred fifty teacher educators selected randomly and engaged in education colleges of Punjab taking into account their financial status. To collect the data from teacher educators, Professional Commitment Scale standardized by Kanchan Kohli (2005) was used. Descriptive statistics was applied to analyse the data. Findings indicate that groups of teacher educators exhibit similar level of professional commitment regardless of their monthly earnings.

Key word : Professional Commitment, Education Colleges, Teacher Educators, Monthly Earnings.

Introduction:

The successful development of any nation depends on the good quality of education. Teachers are the key functionaries of every educational institution with the task of preparing future citizens. Thus, teachers are such important personalities without whom teaching learning process is next impossible. Today, due to fast changing globalized world set up the role of a teacher has become not only substantial but, challenging and demanding. Obviously, he/she is to perform numerous things while working in educational institution. Apart from teaching, the teacher is to remain fully up-to-date with the recent digital technology to be used in the teaching and learning process, maintain coordination between the school, society and management bodies, other extracurricular activities involving control and discipline and effectively coordinating everything to make sure that a healthy and productive environment persists in educational institutions. Of course, these aspects can be well handled by teachers who are skilled, efficient, competent and committed. Now, such teachers are prepared by teacher educators in teacher training colleges. Competent and committed teacher educators alone can develop professional abilities, skills and proper behavioural qualities among the prospective student teachers. It is to be noted that several regulatory bodies time to time are trying their best to enhance the professional quality of teacher educators and fully oriented towards the restructuring and revamping the teacher education programs. In spite of all this, our educational institutions are lagging behind considerably to produce professionally skilled and quality teachers. Timely salary payment along with other financial rewards, undoubtedly, regulates the effectiveness and better job performance among teacher educators with satisfaction. It promotes their retention and help maintaining overall quality in education system. It is in this backdrop, the present paper tries to investigate the professional commitment of teacher educators with respect to their financial status.

Review of the Related Literature:

Shishupal (2001) investigated commitment to teaching profession of B.Ed. prospective teachers and concluded that gender, age, father's occupation, community background and income groups does not influence commitment.

Hussen et al. (2016) attempted to assess the status of school teachers' professional commitment towards their own profession, student learning, and the community of eastern Ethiopian society. The study was conducted on 14 secondary schools and 170 respondents were selected as sample. The finding disclosed that teachers' commitment to learning, towards community and their own profession was affected and characterised as low because of the meagre salary, less incentives, low motivation and respect, and negative attitude towards the teaching profession.

Shoaib and Khalid (2017) studied the professional commitment of 320 teacher educators of GCETs in Punjab province in Pakistan with respect to demographic variables. As regards to the findings specifically related to the influence of income on the professional commitment, it was concluded that teacher educators with more monthly income showed better commitment as compared to those with less monthly income.

Mwesiga and Okendo (2018) examined the levels of commitment of teachers to teaching profession in secondary schools in Kagera region of Tanzania. Findings indicate better commitment among teachers while observing various work responsibilities assigned at job places. But, this tendency declined later due to interrelated issues like lack of training seminars and workshops, professional development programmes, non-participation of teachers in decision making, incompetent head, lack of communication, unhealthy work culture, low salaries, etc.

Brinia et al. (2021) examined the perception of 270 primary education teachers as to how their work effectiveness was related to moral satisfaction, financial gains and ways of motivation. It was concluded that teachers effectiveness was positively and significantly correlated with satisfaction with financial incentives as well as salary satisfaction. These factors contributed much in their increase in their work efficiency.

Ghose (2023) studied the financial incentives and its influence on the quality and performance of private CBSE school teachers of Ahmedabad. The result stated that the academic performance of teachers bears positive and significant relationship with the financial incentives. Proper salary and related allowances motivate the teachers to concentrate on the overall performance of the students as well.

Nithya (2023) studied the commitment of high school teachers of Coimbatore district and found that teachers having a monthly salary of Rs 20000/-and above were more professionally committed than those receiving less than the said amount.

Ahmed (2024) examined the impact of salary on the work performance of secondary school teachers and concluded that teachers who are paid fairly show more dedication towards their duties, more satisfied and motivated with excellent outcome with respect to students concerned.

Perdizo and Tantiado (2025) investigated the financial wellbeing and job satisfaction of 170 teachers working in Cagayan de Oro City Division in Philippines. It was concluded that the factors which counted in job satisfaction of teachers, their retention and best pupil outcome were mainly financial sufficiency and supportive work environment at their institutes.

Ngozi (2025) studied the impact of financial incentive on the teacher commitment and job security in the Delta State in Nigeria by collecting data from 400 teachers and 40 school administrators. The study concluded that financial incentives (salaries, bonuses, other

allowances, etc.) that are equitable and consistent promote teacher retention and quality in education and overall commitment.

Espra and valle (2025) examined the professional commitment of 114 elementary school teachers and their job satisfaction in Medina district, Division of Misamis Oriental, Phillippines. The study concluded that both job satisfaction and professional commitment of teachers are positively and significantly related. Again the professional commitment of teachers bears a positive correlation with salary benefits, overall work culture, job related responsibilities, community attachment, etc.

Objective of the Study:

1. To study the professional commitment of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings.

Hypothesis of the Study:

1. There exists no significant difference in the professional commitment of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings.

Research Method Applied:

The descriptive approach was followed to conduct the present study.

Population and Sample of the study:

All teacher educators working in government, government-aided and self-financed education colleges affiliated to Punjabi University, Panjab University and Guru Nanak Dev University constitute the population of the present study. Professional commitment scale developed by Kanchan Kohli (2005) was utilised to collect the data from 450 teacher educators selected randomly.

Findings with interpretation:

Comparison of the professional commitment of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings was done using t-test to find the difference in their mean professional commitment scores as presented below in table 1.

The findings of t-test for the mean difference in the professional commitment of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings is produced in the Table 1.

Table 1

Analysis for t-test to determine the difference in mean scores of teacher educators on professional commitment with low and high monthly earnings

Monthly Earnings	N	Sum	Sum of Squares	Mean	S.D.	t-value
Low (Up to one Lac)	286	27375	2657327	95.72	11.41	0.13
High (More than one Lac)	164	15717	1528605	95.84	11.71	

The table given above depicts the t-value=0.13 that has been worked out to determine the significant difference, if any, in the mean professional commitment score of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings. This obtained t-value is obviously much less as compared to the critical value of $t=1.965$ for significance at 0.05 level and 448 df. This result indicates that no significant difference exists in the professional commitment of teacher educators having low and high monthly earnings. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that "There exists no significant difference in the professional commitment of teacher educators with low and high monthly earnings" gets accepted.

Discussion of the result:

The current study reveals that teacher educators do not differ significantly in the professional commitment with regard to their monthly earnings. In this connection, the finding of an earlier study performed by Shishupal (2001) "teacher trainees' income groups do not predict the professional commitment significantly" goes in line with the present finding. On the contrary, all other studies included in the section 'review of related literature' of this paper talk about the positive and significant correlation between professional commitment and financial stability of teachers that contradicts the present finding. In perspective of the present finding by the researcher, it may be stated that in view of the job crisis & insecurity and one's professional aspirations, teacher educators have the common tendency to keep themselves engaged with commitment in any institution where they are employed irrespective of their earnings.

Educational Implications

Both the financial stability and job satisfaction, certainly, go a long way to boost the commitment of teacher educators. These two factors, despite professional loyalty and integrity being maintained by teacher educators, help them to perceive their autonomy and motivate them to perform well with positivity. As such, the regulatory bodies in collaboration with stakeholders of education may come up to support the financial health of their subjects, particularly those serving in self-financed education colleges of Punjab where they have, commonly, poor monetary gains. Regular checks and visits of education colleges need to be carried out to monitor various issues related to attendance, discipline, task-allocation, academic outcome, salary-payment, etc. Side by side, it is to be seen that regular programmes are arranged in institutions for professional excellence of teacher educators. Needless to say, all such measures, if adopted effectively, are destined to improve the performance of teacher educators and motivate them to enhance their professional commitment. That is how the practice of imparting quality teacher-education may be promoted to a large extent in institutions concerned.

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